

LEXICO-SEMITIC ANALYSIS OF MODERN BUSINESS TERMS IN ENGLISH

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***Abstract:** In very general terms, Business English is defined as a specialized area of English relating to the language used in business. However, this concise definition may sound too simplistic from a linguistic point of view and will, undoubtedly, lead to a number of questions: Is Business English really a language? Are there any native speakers of Business English? Can we apply linguistic theories to the study of Business English in the same way as we study natural human languages?*

***Key words:** linguistics, ELT, Business English, sociolinguistics, specialist language, variation.*

The aim of the following study is to come to grips with one of the most elusive terms – Business English – from a number of linguistic points of view. I will try to present Business English as a theoretically coherent phenomenon which can be defined as a specialist language. Specialist languages, special languages (SL) or languages for special/specific purposes (SLP) are terms more widely used among practitioners than theorists. Yet, despite their enormous popularity, SL remain a little researched and ill-defined area of applied linguistics (Sobkowiak 2008, Grucza 2009, Lewandowski 2013, Wille 2014). The concept of SL is both usage-oriented and tightly connected to professional practices. SL seem to constitute an

ontologically gradient phenomenon which generates a number of controversies. Some researchers discard SL as a construct for investigation, claiming that instead of languages we are dealing with terminologies. Others maintain that a specialist language includes “the totality of all linguistic means” and should be investigated at all linguistic levels (Hoffmann 1976: 170). Still in other approaches, SL are approached as semi-autonomous variants, jargons, technolects or sub-languages based on expert knowledge. In the cursory survey that follows I will classify these views as either teaching-based, variation-based, terminology-based, discourse-based or language-based. I will argue that treating Business English as a specialist language is fully justified and, as a result, Business English constitutes an interesting subject of study for theoretical as well as applied linguistics.

ESP is a type of ELT (English Language Teaching) which began to emerge in the 1960s as a response to a growing awareness that there were certain types of learners who had specialized needs that General English courses did not meet. Soon this evolving practice of teaching Business English, directly related to learners’ and their employers’ professional needs, started to be accompanied and guided by abundant theoretical literature. I will enumerate only a few examples in a historical order. Thus, Palmer (1964) mentions the selective concentration on particular language skills and abilities as an important characteristic of ESP, Strevens (1977, 1980) offers a comprehensive definition of ESP, Robinson (1980) writes a thorough review of theoretical positions and what ESP meant at that time, Coffey (1985) updates Strevens’s work and puts ESP in the context of communicative language teaching. Generally speaking, all ELT approaches to Business English are utilitarian, practical and goal-oriented. Business English is seen as a process, not as a product. Hutchinson and Waters (1987) believe that Business English and ESP in general should not be perceived as “specialized varieties of English” or as a special form of

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language different in kind from other forms. We can conclude from this cursory overview that in ELT Business English is neither a language, nor a particular kind of language, but it is rather a methodology of designing and running a special-purpose language course. Sobkowiak (2008: 23, 46) believes that Business English is merely a method of teaching “a specific language corpus” and “a particular kind of communication in a specific context”.

Business English does not have to be restricted to the context of teaching English and it does not have to be approached from the classroom perspective of ELT.1 What is more, Business English can be seen as a variety of language existing independent of learners and teachers. Here I will try to defend the view that Business English has naturally evolved into a language variety. Seen from this perspective, Business English constitutes a linguistic and social phenomenon in its own right. One of the characteristic features of a natural human language is the fact that language is constantly changing. We must bear in mind that all living languages experience constant change and this intrinsic property should not be treated as corruption, deterioration or something that can be prevented (Grygiel and Kleparski 2007). Language is a dynamic system and as such it evolves along three basic directions – in time (historically), in space (geographically) and in stratification (socially). The divisions into separate national languages such as English, Polish or German are a direct consequence of this process of variation. Most languages develop a standard form typically associated with the idea of a nation. A recognized national language further comprehends the notion of prestige, usually because those who speak this variety are the richest and most powerful while those who do not speak it are poorer and less powerful. Thus, the standard variety of a language is merely one of its dialects which happens to be in a more favorable position. From the purely linguistic and grammatical point of view, however, all dialects are equally

as developed as the standard variety and equal in status.

The study of Business English must follow the guidelines of applied linguistics in combining linguistic theory with praxis. Notice that this kind of theoretical investigation is not only geared toward enriching our knowledge about the phenomenon in question, but it is also motivated by very practical goal oriented tasks. They can be divided into three basic categories. First of all, the study of Business English can be pedagogically-centered (Sobkowiak 2008). As a result, many of the researchers involved in the investigation of Business English are also active in teaching. The next major area of application is translation (Wille and Pikor-Niedzialek 2014). In this case, rather than language, a more precise object of analysis is a specialist text. Finally, many studies of Business English are prescriptively rather than descriptively guided. This means that their ultimate motivation is to discover how to improve business communication and how to use language to be more successful in achieving one's goals in business rather than simply describe the language of business. Summing up, it is possible to conclude that Business English is investigated not as an end to itself, but largely to inform teaching, translation or training programs. By advocating the thesis that Business English is best described as a specialist language, I also strongly believe that its investigation should remain language-focused, descriptive, research-led and based on a solid linguistic theory.

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